

15th-16th February 2023

PhD Day

2023

Doctorate in Sciences and Technologies of Chemistry and Materials

Wed 15th 15-17
Aula 12

Poster presentations
by 2nd year PhD
students

Thu 16th 10-12
Aula 12

Poster presentations
by 3rd year PhD
students

Thu 16th 14:30-18
Aula magna

Conference by
Prof. James Clark
University of York

Oral presentations by
PhD students

Best poster awards

Department of Chemistry and Industrial Chemistry
Via Dodecaneso 31 – 16146 Genoa

Master students, researchers and all interested people are invited to participate

Porous materials from particle stabilised foams

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Introduction

The research focuses on the development of porous materials based on the direct foaming of nanoparticle (NP) dispersions. Such foams can be consolidated into solid porous structures by suitable chemical and thermal processing, in accordance with the so-called gel-casting method.

The specific aims of the research are:

- Developing solid foams with tailored structural and functional properties from particle-stabilised liquid foams, in particular based on multicomponent Nanoparticle (NP) dispersions, in order to incorporate smart functionalities (ex., photocatalysis).
- Optimising the processing steps towards milder/greener/sustainable production methods (ex., lower processing temperatures, utilisation of environmentally milder chemicals and/or recyclable materials).

Gel-casting method points to great potential with the following main advantages:

- Applicability to virtually any kind of NP, provided to choose a proper surfactant to make these NP amphiphilic.
- Possibility to obtain materials characterized by open cell structure with large specific area and multiscale/hierarchical porosity, very suitable for applications related to fluid flows.
- Relatively simple processing and scalability of the production.
- Possibility to obtain pre-formed porous materials.

The research is performed at CNR-ICMATE (Genova) within the EU MSCA-ITN "Dynamics of dense nanosuspensions: a pathway to novel functional materials - nanoPaint" activities.

Method and materials

1) Gel casting protocol: Strengthening the structure of liquid foams to produce green body.

A. Solid content dispersion.

- Decorated NP dispersion 30%wt + surfactant in proportion 1:1 mixing 2h.
 - Titania NP + CTAB (cetyltrimethylammonium bromide); Glass (borosilicate) NP + CTAB
- Non-decorated NP dispersion 30%wt.
 - Titania NP + CTAB
 - Glass NP

Mixed dispersions of NPs were tried using both decorated and non-decorated NPs in 1:1 or 1:5 proportion.

B. Jelling agent addition

- Poly(vinyl alcohol) (PVA) – aq. sol. at 7.8wt% in 1:1 proportion with solid content dispersion, mixing for 2h at 1000 rpm
- HNO₃ at 69 v% in 1:10 proportion with NP-PVA dispersion, mixing 10min.
- DHF (dimethoxydifurfurane) in 1.2:10 proportion with NP-PVA dispersion, mixing 1min.

C. Foaming for 2 min @ 10000 rpm by Ultraturrax homogeniser.

D. 3 hours at 80°C.

2) High Temperature Treatment: Material consolidation

and removal/burning of organic components.

Results II: TiO₂ + Borosilicate solid foams

To reduce the processing temperature, different changes in the strategy have been proposed and are already being implemented:

- Use of borosilicate glass nanoparticles in combination to titania (binary NP dispersions) to stabilize the foam and give support to the lamella.
- Increase of the solid content in the dispersion (up to 15 wt%).
- Use of new foaming methods, based on controlled gas insufflation, more suitable for dispersions with larger solid content.

Top panels (a and b): two optic microscopy pictures of the "green body" (before high temperature treatment) of a solid foam obtained from mixed NP dispersions (titania NP 30%wt + 2E-3M CTAB and borosilicate NP in proportion 1:5). It presents an open porous structure. Bottom panels: details of pores of the same solid foam obtained after thermal treatment at (c) 600°C and (d) 750°C.

The first results of application of the gel casting method on these mixed dispersions are promising. In particular foams processed at 600 °C show much better mechanical properties. As shown by the SEM pictures, hierarchical porous structuring needs instead to be improved.

Some foams as above under SEM. (a and b) details of foams treated at 600°C (c) foams treated at 750°C

Background

The Gel casting method: From Particle-Stabilized Foams to Porous Materials

Self-organisation in the lamella through the formation of amphiphilic particles

Results I: TiO₂ solid foams

The porous materials obtained from only titania+CTAB dispersions show an interesting hierarchical pore structure, with high specific interfacial area both for treatment temperatures at 600 °C and 900 °C. While those treated at 600 °C are quite fragile for a practical utilisation, acceptable mechanical characteristics are found in the samples treated at 900 °C. Such high temperatures favours however the transition from anatase to the rutile forms TiO₂, with consequent decrease of the photocatalytic features.

Two examples of porous materials obtained from TiO₂ + CTAB dispersions under the SEM observation. Left: TiO₂ 30wt% + CTAB 2.5E-4M, treated at 600°C. Right: TiO₂ 30wt% + CTAB 7.5E-3M, treated at 600°C. The samples show a hierarchical structure with different open porous sizes. The inserts show details of the pores at high magnification, showing the roughened fine structure on the scale of the TiO₂ NP size (200 nm), which ensures a high specific area of the material.

Attempts to overcome the observed problems are based on: i) increasing of the solid content in the dispersions, which requires different foaming methods (ex., insufflation instead of homogeniser); ii) start from a multiple particle dispersion (see Results II), where lower softening NP (ex., glass) may form a backbone for the TiO₂ NPs; iii) both as above.

Conclusions and further work

- 1) The main applications for these titania-based materials are related to photocatalysis, for which the porous materials obtained from titania+CTAB dispersions show an interesting hierarchical pores structure.
- 2) Solid foams obtained from mixed NP systems (titania + glass) are in fact conceived to conjugate acceptable mechanical properties (glass) and functional photocatalytic features (titania). This new formulation has been in fact proposed as an alternative to overcome the poor mechanical properties of the solid foams obtained from dispersion of the sole titania.

Currently, work is being done to optimize the porosity and mechanical properties of this mixed systems foams. This involves:

- Developing an effective foaming method and applying a lower process temperature, preserving the anatase phase of titania.
- Optimise surfactant content/type to obtain suitable and stable foam structure.
- Produce glass NP particles with size comparable with TiO₂ NPs (200 nm) by milling of those available on the market.
- In perspective, soda-lime glass will be tested, in order to reduce even more the processing temperatures and work with recycled glass
- A second system based on chitosan is going to be investigated as alternative route for the stabilisation of foams made from the dispersions, using biocompatible compounds.

References

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